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GEAR AND BEARING DESIGNS WITH LUBRICATED AND REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

A thorough characterization of a series of thermoplastic composites suitable for gears and bearings including static ASTM physical properties such as tensile strength, tensile elongation, flexural strength, flexural modulus, izod impact strength, gear tooth strength, heat distortion temperature and coefficient of linear thermal expansion and long-term resistance to cyclic stress (fatigue endurance) and creep will be presented. Processing parameters including injection pressure, injection rate, melt temperature, and mold temperature will be examined for their effect on gear tooth strength, TIR, and tooth-to-tooth error.

MECHANICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Static ASTM physical and mechanical properties of tensile strength, flexural strength, shear strength, flexural modulus, izod impact strength, gear tooth strength, specific gravity, heat deflection temperature at 264 psi, water absorption, and coefficient of linear thermal expansion are presented in Figure 1 for a series of reinforced and lubricated thermoplastic resins.

Tensile and Flexural Strength

Tensile strength (ASTM D-638) values ranged from a low of 6,500 psi for 20% TFE lubricated polyacetal resin, up to 33,000 psi for 60% glass-fortified 6/6 nylon resin. The glass-fortified nylon compounds are strengthened to the greatest degree, while the fortified polycarbonate, polysulfone, and polyacetal resins also demonstrate increases in tensile strength. Flexural strengths of fortified thermoplastic resins follow much the same pattern, although the level is typically 40 to 50% (ASTM D-790) higher than when stress is uniaxially applied as in the tensile test. The static stress-strain rupture properties such as tensile strength and flexural strength do not predict long-term rupture performance and do not necessarily rank materials in the same order as time-dependent studies. Physical property data detailing the effects of temperature, humidity, straining-rate, and sample geometry on tensile strength and flexural strength for most fiber fortified thermoplastic resin systems are available to the design engineer and should be considered where applicable.

Flexural Modulus

Flexural moduli (ASTM D-790) of thermoplastic resins are dramatically increased with the addition of fiber fortifiers as illustrated in Figure 1. Three-to-five fold increases in flexural modulus can be readily obtained in the thermoplastic resins with the addition of glass fibers. The addition of TFE lubricant also leads to increased modulus values. Flexural modulus values to 2,800,000 psi can be realized with the addition of 60% glass fibers to 6/6 nylon. The flexural modulus data comparison is presented to demonstrate the ability of fortifiers to dramatically increase the rigidity of a series of thermoplastic resins. The modulus data do not consider the effects of time, temperature and straining rate on long-term rigidity, although these data are generally available for most of the reinforced resin systems presented.

Impact Strength

A comparison of impact properties in polymer systems is an uncertain business, further compounded in fortified thermoplastics. The usual variables of polymer type, specimen geometry, notch radius, molding condition, straining rate, and magnitude of applied load is further complicated in fortified thermoplastic polymers by the average fiber length and length distribution, coupling agent used, fiber glass loading level and dispersion of glass fibers. The impact strength data presented in Figure 1 for 1/4" bar samples, demonstrate the increased notched izod impact strengths (ASTM D-256) attained with the addition of fiber reinforcements for some polymer systems (nylon 6/6 and polysulfone), and decreased notched izod impact strengths obtained with many other fiber reinforced polymer systems (polycarbonate and polyacetal).

The unnotched Izod impact strengths of thermoplastic resins are in general reduced by the addition of glass fiber fortifiers and TFE lubricants. The fortified nylon and polycarbonate resins are regarded as the "toughest" of the reinforced thermoplastic resins. The design engineer assures himself of very little in the performance of his part by simply specifying notched and unnotched Izod impact strength values for a resin/fiber fortifier composite. Only prototype testing can give truly conclusive results.

Heat Deflection Temperature

Large increases in heat deflection temperatures (ASTM D-648) are realized in crystalline polymers (polyacetal and nylon 6/6) with the addition of fortifiers, while moderate increases in heat deflection temperatures are realized with fortifier addition to amorphous polymer resins (polycarbonate and polysulfone). Heat deflection temperatures to 500°F at 264 psi (glass-fortified 6/6 nylon) can be attained with glass-fortified thermoplastic resin systems.

Coefficient of Linear Thermal Expansion

The coefficient of linear thermal expansion data presented in Figure 1 for glass-fortified base resins shows them all to lie between 0.9×10^{-5} to 2.7×10^{-5} in./in./°F, while zinc die castings have a typical value of 1.5×10^{-5} in./in./°F.

Shear Strength

The punch-type of shear (ASTM test D-732) generally yields results approximating the tensile yield strength (ASTM D-638) values for unreinforced thermoplastic resins. The lower tensile elongation and increased notch sensitivity of the glass-reinforced thermoplastic resins apparently contributes to limit the increases in shear strength below the large increases noted in other tensile related properties for reinforced thermoplastics.

Tooth Strength of Gears

Tooth strength was determined on injection molded, 20 pitch, 20 degree pressure angle, full depth, 2 1/2-in. pitch diameter, 1/2-in. face-width spur gears and 32 pitch, 20 degree pressure angle, full depth, 2 1/2-in. pitch diameter, 1/8-in. face-width spur gears. A sturtevant torque testing fixture and torque wrench (S-1299-1) were employed in determining tooth strength values. Three teeth per gear were individually engaged and torqued to failure; average values for three gears are given in Figure 1.

A major difficulty associated with tooth strength testing is the variation in applied rate of strain induced by varying molding tolerances due to shrinkage differences, testing rate, and failure modes. No predictable correlation was observed between tooth strength, tensile strength, and shear strength for the TFE lubricant and glass-fortified thermoplastic resins. Scanning electron microphotographs (Figure 2) of gear tooth fracture surfaces torqued to failure, of glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 and glass-reinforced acetal reveal significantly different fracture behavior patterns. The glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 compound SEM's indicate strong adhesion of resin particles to the glass fibers while the glass-reinforced acetal compound SEM's indicate essentially no adhesion (Figure 3).

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LONG-TERM PERMANENCE PROPERTIES

Fatigue Endurance

The behavior of a series of glass-fortified thermoplastic resin systems is described under conditions producing cyclic fatigue failure. While reinforcement of thermoplastic resins greatly increases mechanical properties, the retention of these properties under conditions of large applied stresses for extended periods of time is an equally valuable asset. Fatigue endurance data are presented for a series of TFE lubricated and glass fortified resin systems. The effects of stress, glass fiber content, glass bead filler, TFE lubricant, and base resin on fatigue endurance of several thermoplastic resin systems is examined. Plastics fail under repeated cyclic stress at a level below their static strength. The number of cycles required to cause failure is dependent on stress, temperature, and frequency. The endurance limit is defined as the stress level below which a material will withstand cyclic testing indefinitely. The injection-molded test specimens had a tapered cross section, such that under constant load a uniform stress was produced over the entire length of the beam. Samples were subjected to alternating flexural cycling under constant load at 1800 cycles per minute on a Sonntag Model SF2 per ASTM D-671. The data are presented in the form of S-N curves (logarithmic plots of stress, S, versus the number of cycles to failure, N).

TFE Lubricated Resins

The S-N curve for 20% TFE lubricated polyacetal copolymer (Figure 4) exhibits a well-defined fatigue endurance limit of 2,800 psi, while 20% TFE lubricated 6/6 nylon exhibits the characteristic S-N curve with a fatigue endurance limit value of 3,200 psi. A 15% TFE lubricated, 30% glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 compound exhibits a fatigue endurance limit of 4,650 psi, while a 15% TFE lubricated, 30% glass-reinforced polycarbonate displays a limit of 5,000 psi (Figure 4).

Polycarbonate Resins

A series of glass-reinforced polycarbonate resins exhibited well defined fatigue endurance limits as follows:

- Polycarbonate resin 900 psi
- 20% Glass-reinforced polycarbonate resin 5,000 psi
- 30% Glass-reinforced polycarbonate resin 5,500 psi
- 40% Glass-reinforced polycarbonate resin 6,000 psi
- 30% Glass bead filled polycarbonate resin 3,250 psi

A dramatic increase (5-6 fold) in fatigue endurance limit is achieved with glass-fiber reinforcement of polycarbonate resin. A moderate increase in fatigue endurance limit is noted with the addition of 30% glass beads to polycarbonate resin.

Nylon 6/6 Resins

The addition of glass fiber reinforcement to nylon 6/6 resin leads to large increases in the fatigue endurance limit:

- Nylon 6/6 resin (moisture conditioned) 3,250 psi
 - 30% Glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 resin (moisture conditioned) 5,850 psi
 - 40% Glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 resin (moisture conditioned) 7,000 psi
 - 30% Glass bead filled nylon 6/6 resin (moisture conditioned) 3,850 psi
 - Nylon 6/6 resin (dry as molded) 5,250 psi
 - 30% Glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 resin (dry as molded) 7,700 psi
 - 40% Glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 resin (dry as molded) 9,000 psi
- The addition of glass bead reinforcement to nylon 6/6 resin leads to a modest increase in the fatigue endurance limit (Figure 5).

The effect of moisture conditioning (50% R.H.) on the nylon 6/6 resin series reveals the large decrease (60%) in the fatigue endurance limit of the unreinforced nylon 6/6 resin after conditioning and the relatively smaller decreases (20-30%) noted with the glass-reinforced resins (Figure 5).

Creep

Creep is defined as the total deformation produced in a viscoelastic body by the application of stress. It contains a purely elastic, constant component (the instantaneous value of the modulus of elasticity) and a time-dependent, slowly increasing component, (the creep function). The total deformation under constant load is the sum of these components. Creep data is presented as total strain at a constant applied stress in flexure at 73°F. Curves depicting total strain versus time are presented for nylon 6/6 and polycarbonate resin systems at three levels of applied stress. The effect of glass loading level on the creep characteristics of nylon 6/6 and polycarbonate resins is described in Figures 8&9. For most unreinforced thermoplastics the apparent modulus (applied stress/creep strain) is a function of the applied stress. However, the apparent moduli of glass fiber fortified 6/6 nylon and polycarbonate compounds are independent of stress level up to 5 000 psi. The viscoelastic limit for these materials exceed 5 000 psi. All glass-fortified resin systems exhibit marked improvement over the base resins in their ability to sustain loads when subjected to constant stress.

The reinforced nylon 6/6 and polycarbonate samples approach equilibrium after 100 hours at the lower applied stress levels (1,250 psi, 2,500 psi) and 1000 hours at the 5,000 psi applied stress level (Figures 8&9). The unreinforced nylon 6/6 resin exhibits a substantial creep rate after 1000 hours at 1,250 psi (Figure 9). All glass-fortified resin systems exhibit marked improvement over the base resins in their ability to sustain loads when subjected to constant stress. Earlier studies revealed the ability of glass-fortified resin systems to maintain dimensional stability when subjected to constant loads, even at stress levels that approach the yield strength of the unreinforced resin?

CONSTANT BLEED INTERNALLY LUBRICATED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOUNDS

A variety of high speed bearing and slide applications have accelerated demands for materials with extremely low rates of wear. Sealed bearings are among the many applications requiring maintenance-free service. The solution is to provide continuous boundary lubrication of the mating surface. Traditional internally lubricated thermoplastics (ILTP) require a finite period of time for an internal lubricant to become exposed and then burnish over the wear surface in a wear situation. Although the period of time is quite brief, it does allow for a possible mating in boundary lubrication.

A solution to the demands of maintenance-free service is offered by a new class of internally lubricated materials. These materials are partial alloys of a thermoplastic with a lower molecular weight polymer. The lower molecular weight polymer is selected both on its ability to behave as a boundary lubricant and a limited compatibility with the thermoplastic resin. By alloying the materials at carefully controlled proportions during compounding, a non-particulate composite blend results. The lower molecular weight polymer moves to the surface by two processes—diffusion by random molecular movement and exclusion from the matrix due to its limited compatibility. The net result is the continual generation of a polymer film which behaves as a boundary lubricant. Unlike oil-based lubricants, the surface tensions of polymer lubricants are sufficiently low to allow adhesion to the thermoplastic wear surface. The selection of polymer lubricant and concentration is extremely critical. Although a wide range of polymeric lubricants are available such as the polysiloxanes, polyphenylene ethers, and perfluoroalkylethers, only specific lubricants at specific concentrations are compatible with a given thermoplastic resin.

A further enhancement of wear properties may be achieved by combining polymer bleed lubrications with solid internal lubricants. As these materials reach the wear interface together they behave as high temperature greases. The solid lubricant behaves both as a

thickener and as an extreme pressure additive. The polymeric lubricant insures unbroken lubricity at high speeds.

A comparison of silicone constant bleed compounds containing PTFE internal lubricant and ILTP's containing only PTFE is outlined in Figure 10. It can be seen that wear factor and friction are generally reduced 30-50%. The K factor for the nylon based ILTP's is in the same range as PTFE compounds. The addition of constant bleed agents had the greatest effect on LPV at high velocities. This is to be expected since high speed failure is more directly related to wear. In acetal, for example the PV limit was more than doubled at 1000 fpm in comparison to a straight PTFE based material. The ability of the silicone to continually replenish hydrodynamic boundary lubrication accounts for the dramatic decrease in wear of CB compounds at high speeds. Injection-moldable constant bleed ILTP's can be expected to replace filled PTFE in many applications where process economy and dimensional stability are important features.

WEAR AND FRICTIONAL PROPERTIES

Since their introduction over ten years ago, internally lubricated thermoplastics have penetrated a large variety of gear and bearing applications. The displacement of metal forerunners has not been predicated on processing or material economy but on performance characteristics. Reduced maintenance, quiet running (a consequence of vibration dampening), light weight and resistance to hydrolytic corrosion have been contributing factors. The materials excel in metal mating applications. Finally, the introduction of reinforcing fillers has removed previous deficiencies in mechanical strength, dimensional stability, and thermal expansion.

Under conditions of optimum lubrication mating materials are separated by a lubricant layer. The frictional characteristics are determined by viscosity in the case of a liquid lubricant or shear strength in the case of a solid lubricant. In normal wear and particularly under stop-start, load pulsing, or oscillatory conditions the boundary may be broken. In these circumstances, the mating surfaces come into direct contact. The ability to maintain boundary lubrication and the intrinsic compatibility of the materials determines mode of failure. Mating interaction is defined by two factors—wear and friction—which are not simply related. Reduction in both friction and wear account in part for the increased utility of internally lubricated thermoplastics.

The composition of internally lubricated thermoplastics is complex in comparison to other engineering materials. In a basic system a lubricating component is incorporated into a thermoplastic matrix to form a simple composite. In a more advanced system, reinforcing fillers are additionally incorporated to lend strength and stability to the composite. Finally, combinations of different lubricants may be incorporated to extend the range of wear resistance to stop-start or extreme pressure etc.

The frictional properties of ILTP's vary in a unique way from metals. In contrast to metals, the thermoplastic matrix possesses a low modulus. The microscopic result is a material with much less rigidity than metal. PTFE, the thermoplastic agent responsible for lubricity in many of the modified thermoplastics has a compressive modulus of only 60,000 psi, compared to 30,000,000 psi for mild steel. Because thermoplastics are not rigid bodies they do not behave according to the classical laws of friction. In the model often presented for metal-metal friction, the irregular microstructure of the surfaces slide against one another. An asperity may shear the boundary lubricant film and weld to its mating surface or it may interlock with or plow through mating surface asperities. In contrast, metal-thermoplastic friction is characterized by adhesion (metal and plastic can't weld) and deformation (rather than plowing). This difference in mechanism of friction generation results in a frictional force which is not directly

proportional to load. For thermoplastics the coefficient of friction decreases with increasing load. Also, the coefficient of friction of thermoplastics increases with increasing speed due to their decreasing ability to form a creep region around asperities. Thus the differences in frictional characteristics lead reasonably to the conclusion that ILTP's will have better frictional characteristics than metals. PTFE a high lubricity additive in ILTP's is exemplary of these properties.

Wear is a more complex phenomenon than friction. While coefficient of friction for materials varies over two orders of magnitude. Materials with low coefficients of friction can demonstrate high wear (like PTFE) and vice-versa. Wear rate is generally defined as the volumetric loss of material over a unit of time. Several mechanisms operate in the removal of material from a wear interface. Catastrophic decay of a gear or bearing material is the condition of severe wear when large fragments are lost due to surface fatigue. Given a well-designed part, it is adhesive wear which concerns the design engineer. Under conditions of adhesive wear, fine polymer-powder is gradually removed from the mating surface. Under the general term of adhesive wear four mechanisms operate. Scuffing or adhesive wear is due to the high pressures and intense heating developed during collision of asperities (for metals in adhesive wear temperatures as high as 1000°C at the mating surfaces have been determined). Under these conditions thermoplastics melt and adhere to the harder surface. If a thermoplastic is mating against itself, asperities will microweld then break by shearing action. Plowing wear is prevalent if one of the mating surfaces is harder than the other. The asperities of the harder material cut through the softer material. The plowing effect is reduced in thermoplastics compared to metals due to plastic flow around plow asperities rather than permanent deformation. Corrosive wear is due to the gradual degradation of the plastic surface through oxidation and chain scission. The embrittled layer is removed quickly in a wear interface. Unlike metals, hydrolytically induced corrosive wear is not a problem in plastics. Abrasive wear occurs when foreign particles enter the wear interface and abrade one or both surfaces depending on their hardness. Thermoplastics mitigate the effect of abrasive particles by two mechanisms: 1) at initial impingement at high angles of incidence the thermoplastic can distribute the stress more readily than a metal because of its lower rigidity 2) the particles can be embedded within the plastic below the wear interface.

Several factors account for the deficiencies of neat plastic gears and bearings. Conditions of only moderate sliding pressure are sufficient to result in high wear rates when a thermoplastic mates with itself due to the relatively mild conditions of temperature required to fuse asperities. In general, thermoplastics are difficult to wet (low critical surface tensions). It is therefore difficult to provide a boundary lubricant which will wet the mating surface. The lack of mechanical strength and dimensional stability curtails design of minimum interference parts such as gear teeth. Internally lubricated thermoplastics satisfy the first two deficiencies. Reinforced internally lubricated thermoplastics satisfy all three deficiencies.

PTFE—polytetrafluoroethylene has the lowest coefficient of friction (0.04-0.06) of the internal lubricants like molybdenum disulfide (0.12) and graphite (0.09) which are incorporated into thermoplastic resins. It has a lower static coefficient of friction than dynamic coefficient of friction insuring non-stick-slip properties. It requires little shear energy to form a soft continuous film of lubricant. It possesses an extremely low critical surface tension (18.5 dynes/cm) and consequently has high release properties. These factors account for its performance advantage in internally lubricated thermoplastics.

During break-in wear, PTFE particles embedded in the thermoplastic matrix are sheared and form a high lubricity film over the mating surface. Because of PTFE's extremely high molecular weight, frictional energy at the wear interface does not effect significant changes in

viscosity until temperatures over 300°C are achieved. This contrast with oil-based lubricants which exhibit dramatic viscosity drop and often degrade at temperatures lower than 300°C. The incorporation of PTFE into the resin matrix insures rapid reformation of the boundary lubricant layer should a momentary break occur. Because of PTFE's extremely low critical surface tension it will adhere preferentially to a thermoplastic resin rather than a metal. This results in less opportunity for boundary lubricant removal from the wear interface by transport on a metal surface. This is the reverse of oil lubrication in which adhesion to the metal surface is preferred due to the oil's inability to wet the thermoplastic. PTFE serves to cushion asperities from shock and subsequent fatigue due to its lower elastic modulus, a dramatic example is the 95% reduction of nylon 6/6 wear with incorporation of 20% PTFE resin.

Of the several reinforcements added to thermoplastics, glass fibers due to their overall performance profile have penetrated the greatest range of applications. With the introduction of glass fibers, shrinkage and dimensional stability are generally enhanced by a factor of two-three facilitating design of close tolerance parts. It might be anticipated that the hard, high modulus fibers would accelerate wear processes, but in all cases where the thermoplastic is optimally reinforced, wear factors remain relatively constant. This is attributed to the binding of the thermoplastic to the fiberglass and the increased tenacity of fiberglass for water molecules which contributes to an adsorptive lubricant layer.

Wear and Friction

The long-term efficiency of boundary lubrication ILTP's determines wear rate. Wear rate is measured as the volume of sample material lost during a period of time as the sample travels a given velocity under load. Since variation in plastic hardness was not found to vary wear significantly under operating conditions, the term for hardness has been omitted. Thus, "K" factor appears as a dimensioned constant. Results are reported as "K" factors 10^{-10} in ³min./ft./lb./hour. In this investigation the thrust washer (face I.D. 0.900"-0.905", face O.D. 1.120"- 1.125") was utilized. Determinations were made at 50"/min. under 40 psi load. The mating material was SAE 1040 steel finished to 12 RMS. The conditions were below the PV limit for all composites tested. It has been found that in cases where the PV limit is not approached, wear is relatively independent of velocity and loading. Conditions of ambient temperature and humidity as well as surface finish have been found to effect values.

The reduction of wear and friction upon addition of PTFE to thermoplastics has been well documented. For example, addition of 5% PTFE to nylon 6/6 resulted in a wear reduction of 70%. Increasing the loading to 20% PTFE reduced the wear 95%, results are detailed in Figure 11.

The situation becomes more complicated if a reinforcement as well as the lubricant is present. The addition of glass fibers results in a reduction of wear over virgin resin. This is indicated in Figure 11 for nylon 6/6 with 0, 10, 30, 40, & 50% glass fibers. The reduction in wear is not as great at 50% glass loading as is that from 10% PTFE loadings. The addition of PTFE to glass fibers composites results in reduction of wear to a level comparable to the PTFE alone. Thus, polysulfone with 15% PTFE and 30% glass fibers has a wear factor of 55, close to the 45 observed for polysulfone with 25% PTFE only, and below the 82 observed for polysulfone with 40% glass fibers.

The low wear rates of ILTP's coupled with their low coefficient of frictions account for their adoption in preference to metal forerunners. But where plastic gears and bearings were employed predominantly in metal mating applications five years ago, they are now more often mated with other plastic gears and bearings. Since fusion between plastic asperities occurs, plastic-plastic wear rate is generally much higher than plastic-metal wear rate. As an example the "K" factor for acetal wear against metal is 65, while acetal against

itself has a "K" factor of 10,200. For a gear this is the difference between a life-time of years as opposed to months. Fortunately this problem is eliminated in the case of ILTP's by the presense of the PTFE boundary lubricant which eliminates direct plastic-plastic interaction. Thus, while nylon vs. nylon generates a "K" wear factor over 1150, nylon with 20% PTFE vs. nylon with 20% PTFE has a "K" factor of 30. An even better solution, is to mate one internally lubricated plastic against another. The wear of nylon 6/6 with 20% PTFE (RL4040) against acetal with 20% PTFE (Fulton 404) is only 12.

LIMITING PRESSURE VELOCITY

The short-term efficiency of boundary lubrication of ILTP's was determined by the limiting pressure-velocity (LPV) test. Limiting pressure-velocity determines the extreme conditions of bearing failure while minimizing the contribution of wear. For thermoplastics without internal lubrication, failure is generally through break-down of boundary lubricant. The fusion of asperities can result either in excessive torque or excessive heating. If optimum lubrication is maintained, failure occurs by "cold flow" or "creep" of the material under applied stress.

Experimentally a 1" I.D., 0.060" wall, 1" in length half-journal sample bearing was step-loaded at constant velocity. At each step the sample was allowed to equilibrate as indicated by torque and temperature measurements. The sample was inspected at each load increment. If excessive torque develops, temperature exceeds 300°F on the outside diameter of the plastic bearing or if it exhibits cold-flow, the material is said to have exceeded its PV limit. The PV product at which it last stabilized is designated the limiting pressure-velocity for that material at that specific velocity. Although results are not simply transferable to other sample configurations, the test provides information useful for comparing thermoplastic resins.

Predicting the effects of the addition of PTFE, reinforcing glass fibers, and combinations of these on LPV is not simple. The addition of glass fibers alone at glass fiber loadings up to 50%, generally increases the LPV of a thermoplastic resin at all velocities, since the coupling of the resin to the glass results in a larger shear energy requirement for removing the resin, and the glass itself is a harder bearing material. The increased heat deflection temperature of GRTP's allows bearings to withstand higher temperature without failure. The greatest improvement in LPV, however, is always at lower velocities. It is at low velocities that the PV limit of thermoplastics is dependent on their load carrying ability. The increased modulus and reduced creep of reinforced thermo-plastics allows a greater applied loading before cold-flow occurs. With nylon 6/6 the addition of 30% glass fibers results in a 400% improvement in LPV at 10 ft./min. and an improvement of about 350% at 100 ft./min. and 1000 ft./min.

The effect of PTFE addition is to enhance boundary lubrication. LPV is increased at all velocities. At comparable volume loadings PTFE addition results in higher PV limits than glass fibers. Since only a moderate increase in modulus and creep resistance is effected, it is primarily by functioning as a boundary lubricant that PTFE increases PV limits. Internally lubricated thermoplastics excel at high speeds. At 100 fpm the LPV of nylon 6/6 containing 20% PTFE is increased 1300%.

The addition of both glass fibers and PTFE results in bearing properties that frequently reflect a synergism since the deficiencies of both materials are removed. Thus for nylon 6/6 with 15% PTFE and 30% glass fibers an increase of approximately 1000% in LPV at all velocities is observed. Since the PTFE and glass fiber fillers excel at the extremes of wear (1000 fpm) and load (10 fpm), respectively, LPV's at intermediate speeds and loads are generally improved the most. Figure 12).

PROCESSING

The economic advantages, design versatility and production efficiencies associated with injection molding make it ideally suited for mass producing large numbers of like precision parts. Gears are no exception. In almost all circumstances a finished gear cost less when injection molded from a thermoplastic than when manufactured by any other process. For this reason any gear which has to be produced in large numbers will in all likelihood be considered for injection molding. The continuous improvement in reinforced and modified compounds has opened application areas previously closed to plastics because of mechanical and environmental limitations. As these gear applications become more sophisticated and demanding the design engineer becomes more and more concerned with the manufacturing process, i.e. the injection molding process. The three primary questions raised by the engineer are:

1. How is the accuracy of a gear affected by the various filler systems and base resins?
 2. How do variations in the molding process affect dimensional accuracy?
 3. What effect does the injection molding process have on the physical and mechanical properties of a finished gear?
- The following section of this paper will concern itself with at least partially answering these questions.

The most widely accepted standard for evaluating the accuracy of course (0.5P*-19.9P) and fine (20P-200P) gears (plastic or otherwise) is the classification system established by the American Gear Manufacturers Association (AGMA). The vast majority of plastic gears are fine-pitch and for this reason we will limit our discussion to this type of gearing. Under this system the gear to be checked is rolled against a mating metal master gear in a variable center-distance fixture.

Any variation in the center-line distance can be observed on a dial indicator, or can be charted as shown below.

The total variation in distance is known as the total composite error (TCE). The TCE is made up of two components—the runout and the tooth-to-tooth error (TTE). The TTE is comprised of the pitch and profile errors. The combinations of TTE and TCE have been grouped by the AGMA into classes. The higher the class number the more accurate the gear. In order for a gear to qualify as a class "8" gear its TCE must be between 0.0014" and 0.0019" and the tooth-to-tooth error should be between 0.007" and 0.0010". These classifications are further subdivided according to number of teeth, pitch diameter, and diametral pitch. Class "8" gears of different size will have different allowable TTE and TCE. A perfect gear would of course generate a straight line chart when run against a perfect master gear, however the three primary sources of error discussed above exist to some degree in all gears. Generally speaking, the class of an injection molded plastic gear is dictated by the amount of runout. The TTE is normally well within the dimensional limitations of its particular AGMA classification.

The primary restriction to injection molding high tolerance gears is non-uniform flow in the mold cavity. This non-uniformity of flow

coupled with the anisotropic shrinkage characteristics of the plastic composites are the main cause of poor dimensional reproducibility (i.e. large TCE). It is often stated that due to their low modulus values, plastic gears do not have to be as accurate as non-yielding metal gears. This is an erroneous statement as TTE and TCE in plastic gears can cause excessive noise and wear and can contribute to premature tooth failure caused by excessively high fatigue stress due to the increased tooth deflection. In order to produce a high quality gear, the restrictions discussed above, non-uniform flow and isotropic shrinkage, must be overcome. The design engineer and injection molder have three major variables which when properly controlled will minimize these restrictions and enable him to mold a gear with the required dimensional accuracy.

- A. Mold design
- B. Material selection—
 1. Resin type
 2. Filler type
 3. Filler amount
- C. Molding parameters

The design principles which go into the making of a mold designed to produce a high quality gear are commonly known, but, because of economics or design restrictions, they cannot always be followed. Some of these variables are listed below:

1. Centrally located gates.
2. Uniform and adequate ejector systems.
3. Accurate machining techniques.
4. Proper cooling systems.
5. High quality mold metals.
6. Balanced and properly designed runner systems.
7. Accurately calculated shrinkage characteristics.

The art and techniques of mold making go beyond the scope of this paper, however, a good gear can't be made from a poorly designed mold regardless of the material selection or the molding parameters. A more complete discussion of this facet of plastic gears can be found in other references such as "Accurate Molded Plastic Gears".⁴

In order to evaluate the effect of different resins and filler systems on the molded accuracy of a gear, various thermoplastic composites were injection molded into a gear cavity and checked for dimensional accuracy. The results of this testing are compared in Figure 13. The gear chosen for this test was in all cases a 32 pitch, 20° pressure angle, 1.25 inch pitch diameter, 0.125 inch width spur gear with a 32 pitch, 0.375 inch pitch diameter, 0.18 inch width pinion gear centrally located on the face of the larger gear (see Figure 14). Only the larger gear was checked for dimensional accuracy.

A cavity with a shrinkage of 0.004 in./in. was used for the low shrinkage materials and a cavity with a shrinkage rate of 0.015 in./in. was used for the higher shrinkage materials. It should be noted that the shrinkage of gear cavities should exactly match the shrinkage of the material being used if the TTE is to be minimized. Due to the large number of materials being tested this was impossible. In some cases this mis-match in shrinkage rates leads to larger than normal TTE, however, as stated above, the runout and not the TTE controls the accuracy of a plastic gear. With AGMA classifications of "10" or better the TTE starts to become critical.

To isolate the effect of the various resins and fillers a gear with a single off-center gate was chosen. As will be seen later this is not the optimal gate design for accurately molded gears, however, a large number of gears are gated in this manner because of design restrictions or economics considerations. As shown in Figure 14 the material flows into the cavity around the core pin and then flows radially out from the center along the weld line. The base resins chosen were polycarbonate and nylon 6/6. These are two popular gear materials

(*P=Diametral pitch)

and are representative of the two major types of thermoplastic resins - the high shrinkage, crystalline materials (nylons, acetals, and olefins) and the low shrinkage, amorphous materials (polycarbonates, polysulfones, ABS, and SAN). The gears were molded on an Arburg Model 100 screw injection molding machine using typical molding conditions. The molding conditions were held constant for each base resin regardless of their filler type or content.

The data clearly indicate that the amorphous resins can be molded more accurately than the crystalline materials. This point is vividly illustrated by comparing the tolerance charts for the 6/6 nylon composites (Figure 15, 17, 19) to the corresponding polycarbonate compounds (Figure 16, 18, 20). Inspection of Figure 15 & 16 indicate that the glass fibers align themselves in the direction of flow (along the weld line opposite the gate) causing less shrinkage (a high spot or hump on the gear) in the flow direction than in the transverse direction. By comparing Figure 15 to Figure 17 it can be seen that the glass bead filled 6/6 nylon demonstrates this same anisotropic shrinkage characteristic but to a far lesser degree, and therefore, yields a higher quality gear than the fiberglass reinforced equivalent. The 30% glass bead filled polycarbonate had little or no anisotropic shrinkage and produced an extremely accurate gear (see Figure 18). The TFE lubricated composite shrinks more in the flow direction than in the transverse direction. Because of this shrinkage phenomena the TFE lubricated nylon 6/6 gear had a low spot in the area opposite the gate (see Figure 21)). It can be seen by comparing the TCE Figure 15 to Figure 19 that the TVE lubricated G/R compounds are more accurate than the straight G/R compounds. This is probably due to the fact that the opposite shrinkage characteristics of the two fillers offset each other. It can be readily seen by observing Figures 15 through 21 that the vast majority of the TCE is due to filler orientation in the area 180° from the gate. If the mold had been disc-gated to provide completely uniform flow in the radial direction, then gears with AGMA numbers of "8" or better could have been produced with each of the thermoplastic composites investigated.

The next area to be investigated is molding parameter and their effect on tolerance levels. The same gear described above was molded in an Arburg Model 100 under standard molding conditions (see Figure 22). The TCE and TTE of the gears was then checked as described. One of the molding parameters was then increased or decreased while all other parameters were constant. The change in the TTE and TCE of the gear produced in this manner was then checked and recorded. The results of this testing are summarized in Figure 23. As seen above the tolerances of fiberglass reinforced gears are the most sensitive to variations in shrinkage caused by non-uniform flow. As filler orientation and flow in the cavity are directly related to molding parameters, a crystalline glass fiber reinforced resin and an amorphous glass fiber reinforced resin composite were selected. These data indicated that the amorphous composite produces a consistently high quality gear which is relatively insensitive to changes in molding parameters. Increasing the stock temperature had the most effect on the TCE of the G/R polycarbonate gears. An increase of 40°F in melt temperature caused a 30% improvement in TCE and TTE (see Figure 24). This fact coupled with the small increases in TCE caused by increased injection pressure and lower mold temperature, indicate that G/R amorphous resins produce higher quality gears when they are molded under conditions which place the minimum amount of shear on the resin during molding. This is further reinforced by the fact that molding without a cushion (hence little or no holding pressure) and lowering the injection pressure caused little or no increase in TCE.

While the filling of the cavity seems to dictate the end quality of an amorphous gear, the crystalline materials seem to be most affected by those parameters which control the solidifying of the molten material

in the gear cavity. Shortening the holding time increasing the mold temperature, and molding without a cushion caused significant increases in TCE. Molding conditions which maintain pressure on the material while it is cooling and allow the material to cool quickly, produce the higher quality gears. Molding in this manner lowers the shrinkage in the transverse direction and minimizes the anisotropic shrinkage caused by the fiber orientation. Those molding parameters which lower molded-in stresses and minimize fiber orientation also tend to produce a better gear (i.e. a slow injection rate is better than a fast injection rate). However, the improvements are not as significant as those produced by changes in the parameters which control the cooling portion of the cycle. This explains why increasing the stock temperature increases TCE. While it minimizes stresses it increases the cooling time.

The gears molded for the molding parameter test were gated with two additional gates located 120° from the single gate. All gates were an equal distance from the center of the gear. It can be seen from Figure 25 that the addition of the two gates resulted in a gear with three humps instead of one in the runout curve. These humps are again caused by radial fiber orientation along the weld lines between the gates. It can readily be seen from the comparison that although the three gate system produced three humps, each was significantly smaller than the hump caused by the single gate and therefore the quality of the gear is dramatically improved. The three gate system is getting closer and closer to providing the optimum condition of concentrically uniform flow which would be realized the gear had been disc-gated.

The last question to be answered is what effect can the molder, through variations in molding conditions, have on the mechanical performance of the gear. The gears which were molded under the various molding conditions discussed above were also tested for gear tooth strength. The results of this testing are shown in Figure 26. These data indicate that normal changes in molding parameters cause no significant change in gear tooth strength. None of the variations in molding conditions caused more than a 10% variation in the strength of the gear. These data seem to indicate that those conditions which caused high shear (fiber orientation) in the radial direction yielded gears with slightly higher tooth strengths. It can be seen from the data that the slow injection rate yielded the lowest tooth strength values. More testing would be needed before this trend could be substantiated.

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Figure 1

PROPERTIES OF LUBRICATED AND REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Base Resin	UMP Series Code	Glass Content wt. %	IFF Content wt. %	Specific Gravity	Water Absorption 24 hr. %	Mold Shrinkage in/in	Iron Impact ft. lbs/in (1/4" bar) notched	Flexural Strength 10 ³ psi	Flexural Modulus 10 ⁴ psi	Flexural Strength psi	Tensile Yield Strength psi	Shear Strength psi	Tensile Yield Strength psi	100% Elongation Strength psi	Modulus Deflection Temperature (264 psi) °F	Coefficient of Linear Thermal Expansion 10 ⁻⁵ in/in/°F
				D-792	D-570	D-955	D-256	D-780	D-780	D-790	D-638	D-732	D-638	LIH935	D-646	D-696
Polycarbonate	D 1000	0	0	1.20	0.15	0.0070	>80.0	340	340	13,500	9,500	8,500	9,500	23,500	265	3.75
Polycarbonate	DF 1004	20	0	1.34	0.09	0.0040	17.0	650	650	25,000	16,000	8,600	16,000	27,000	300	1.90
Polycarbonate	UF 1006	30	0	1.43	0.07	0.0075	17.0	1,200	1,200	28,000	18,500	9,400	18,500	29,400	300	1.25
Polycarbonate	UF 1006B	30	0	1.43	0.10	0.0040	5.0	550	550	14,000	6,500	7,000	6,500	20,900	275	2.75
Polycarbonate	UF 1008	40	0	1.52	0.06	0.0020	18.0	1,500	1,500	30,000	21,000	9,900	21,000	32,000	300	1.00
Polycarbonate	DFL4036	30	15	1.55	0.06	0.0015	12.0	1,200	1,200	21,500	17,500	7,500	17,500	25,500	290	1.90
Polysulfone	G 1000	0	0	1.24	0.20	0.0070	>80.0	390	390	15,400	10,200	9,000	10,200	20,000	345	3.10
Polysulfone	GF 1004	20	0	1.38	0.20	0.0075	17.0	850	850	21,000	15,000	9,000	15,000	20,500	360	1.70
Polysulfone	GF 1006	30	0	1.45	0.20	0.0075	14.0	1,200	1,200	24,000	18,000	9,500	18,000	21,000	565	1.40
Polysulfone	GF 1008	40	0	1.55	0.18	0.0070	16.0	1,600	1,600	27,000	20,000	10,000	20,000	22,000	270	1.20
Polysulfone	GF 1008B	30	15	1.59	0.10	0.0050	9.0	1,750	1,750	22,500	15,500	7,500	15,500	25,600	330	1.60
Polyacetal	K 1000	0	0	1.41	0.22	0.0180	>80.0	375	375	15,000	8,800	7,700	8,800	19,600	230	4.70
Polyacetal	KF 1006	30	0	1.63	0.50	0.0050	5.5	1,300	1,300	17,500	13,000	8,200	13,000	23,000	325	2.40
Polyacetal	Fulcon 404	0	20	1.55	0.15	0.0160	4.0	350	350	10,000	6,500	6,000	6,500	9,500	370	2.50
Nylon 6/6	R 1000	0	0	1.14	1.50	0.0180	>80.0	410	410	15,000	11,800	9,600	11,800	23,500	150	4.50
Nylon 6/6	RF 1002	10	0	1.21	1.10	0.0150	5.5	650	650	20,000	14,000	10,000	14,000	25,000	485	2.70
Nylon 6/6	RF 1006	30	0	1.37	0.90	0.0055	2.0	1,500	1,500	38,000	26,000	12,500	26,000	33,400	470	1.80
Nylon 6/6	RF 1006B	30	0	1.37	0.70	0.0060	6.0	600	600	25,000	16,200	6,800	16,200	22,000	175	2.70
Nylon 6/6	RF 1008	40	0	1.46	0.60	0.0050	2.5	1,600	1,600	42,000	31,000	12,700	31,000	35,300	500	1.40
Nylon 6/6	RF 100-12	90	0	1.70	0.40	0.0030	20.0	2,800	2,800	50,000	33,000	13,800	33,000	35,600	500	0.80
Nylon 6/6	RL 4040	0	20	1.26	1.00	0.0140	10.0	300	300	13,800	9,000	6,300	9,000	15,000	220	3.50
Nylon 6/6	RF 4036	30	15	1.49	0.50	0.0045	16.0	1,350	1,350	32,000	23,500	9,700	23,500	31,000	490	2.40

ASTM Method

Fig. 2. Scanning Electron Microphotographs of the Fracture Surface of a Glass-Reinforced Nylon 6/6 Gear Tooth.

Fig. 3. Scanning Electron Microphotographs of the Fracture Surface of a Glass-Reinforced Polyacetal Gear Tooth.

Figure 11

WEAR AND FRICTIONAL PROPERTIES OF THERMOELASTIC RESINS AND COMPOSITES

Base Resin	LNP Series Code	PTFE Lubricant wt. %	Glass Content wt. %	K Factor* (10 ⁻¹⁰ in ³)(min) (ft)(lb)(hr)	Coefficient of Friction*	
					Static 40 psi	Dynamic 40 psi, 50'/min
Styrene-Acrylonitrile	B 1000	—	—	3,000	0.28	0.33
Styrene-Acrylonitrile	BL 4030	15	—	200	0.11	0.14
Styrene-Acrylonitrile	BL 4036	15	30	65	0.13	0.18
Polycarbonate	D 1000	—	—	2,500	0.31	0.38
Polycarbonate	DL 4030	15	—	75	0.09	0.15
Polycarbonate	DFL4036	15	30	30	0.18	0.20
Polycarbonate	DFL4038	15	40	45	0.20	0.23
Polysulfone	GL 4030	15	—	46	0.10	0.09
Polysulfone	GFL4036	15	30	55	0.12	0.10
Polysulfone	GF 1008	—	40	82	0.24	0.20
Acetal	K 1000	—	—	65	0.14	0.21
Acetal	KL 4010	5	—	40	0.12	0.18
Acetal	KL 4020	10	—	30	0.10	0.17
Acetal	KL 4015	15	—	20	0.07	0.15
Acetal	Fulton 404	20	—	17	0.07	0.15
Acetal	KFL4036	15	30	200	0.20	0.28
Acetal (mated against Acetal K1000)	K 1000	—	—	10,200	0.19	0.15
Acetal (mated against nylon 6/6 RL4040)	Fulton 404	20	—	30	0.03	0.04
Polypropylene	ML 4040	20	—	41	0.05	0.11
Polypropylene	MFL4036	15	30	36	0.09	0.09
Nylon 6	P 1000	—	—	200	0.22	0.26
Nylon 6	PL 4030	15	—	15	0.09	0.19
Nylon 6	PFL4036	15	30	17	0.20	0.25
Nylon 6/10	QFL4036	15	30	15	0.23	0.31
Nylon 6/6	R 1000	—	—	200	0.20	0.28
Nylon 6/6	RL 4010	5	—	60	0.13	0.20
Nylon 6/6	RL 4040	20	—	12	0.10	0.18
Nylon 6/6	RFL4036	15	30	16	0.19	0.26
Nylon 6/6	RF 1002	—	10	80	0.17	0.16
Nylon 6/6	RF 1006	—	30	75	0.21	0.20
Nylon 6/6	RF 1008	—	40	70	0.22	0.21
Nylon 6/6	RF100-12	—	60	44	0.23	0.21
Nylon 6/6 (mated against nylon 6/6 R1000)	R 1006	—	—	1,150	0.12	0.11
Nylon 6/6 (mated against nylon 6/6 RL4040)	RL 4040	—	—	30	0.08	0.05
Nylon 6/6 (mated against acetal K1000)	R 1000	—	—	49	0.04	0.05
Nylon 6/6 (mated against acetal Fulton 404)	RL 4040	20	—	12	0.03	0.04
Polyurethane	T 1000	—	—	340	0.32	0.37
Polyurethane	TFL4036	15	30	35	0.20	0.25
Polyester (PBT)	WFL4036	15	30	20	0.16	0.21
Chlorotrifluoroethylene	FC 800	—	—	110	0.54	0.51
Chlorotrifluoroethylene	FC 330	15	—	14	0.14	0.17
Ethylene-Tetrafluoroethylene (Tefzel®)	FC 655	—	25	16	0.24	0.28
Ethylene-Tetrafluoroethylene	FC 685	15	25	11	0.16	0.14
Polyphenylene Sulfide (Ryton®)	PDX 576	—	—	540	0.30	0.24
Polyphenylene Sulfide	PDX 516	15	0	110	0.17	0.15

Figure 12

LIMITING PRESSURE VELOCITY PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC RESINS AND COMPOSITES

Base Resin	LNP Series Code	PTFE Lubricant wt. %	Glass Content wt. %	Limiting PV (journal half bearing)		
				10 ft/min	100 ft/min	1000 ft/min
Styrene-Acrylonitrile	B 1000	—	—	500	300	—
Styrene-Acrylonitrile	BL 4030	15	—	20,000	5,000	3,000
Styrene-Acrylonitrile	BFL4036	15	30	17,500	10,000	10,000
Polycarbonate	D 1000	—	—	750	500	—
Polycarbonate	DFL4036	15	30	27,500	30,000	14,000
Polycarbonate	DFL4038	15	40	20,000	22,500	10,000
Polysulfone	GFL4036	15	30	20,000	35,000	15,000
Acetal	K 1000	—	—	4,000	3,500	<2,500
Acetal	Fulton 404	20	—	10,000	12,500	5,500
Acetal	KFL4036	15	30	12,500	12,000	8,000
Polypropylene	ML 4040	20	—	12,500	5,000	3,000
Polypropylene	MFL4036	15	30	14,000	12,000	7,500
Nylon 6	PFL4036	15	30	17,500	20,000	13,000
Nylon 6/10	QFL4036	15	30	20,000	15,000	12,000
Nylon 6/6	R 1000	—	—	3,000	2,500	<2,500
Nylon 6/6	RF 1006	30	—	12,500	10,000	7,500
Nylon 6/6	RL 4010	5	—	12,500	7,500	3,000
Nylon 6/6	RL 4040	20	—	14,000	27,500	8,000
Nylon 6/6	RFL4036	15	30	17,500	20,000	17,000
Polyurethane	T 1000	—	—	2,000	1,500	—
Polyurethane	TFL4036	15	30	7,500	10,000	5,500
Polyester	WFL4036	15	30	20,000	30,000	5,500
Chlorotrifluoroethylene	FC 800	—	—	1,750	2,150	<1,000
Chlorotrifluoroethylene	FC 830	15	—	17,500	12,500	6,500
Ethylene-Tetrafluoroethylene (Tefzel®)	FC 655	—	25	7,500	10,000	13,000
Polyphenylene Sulfide (Ryton®)	PDX 576	—	—	2,500	3,000	4,000
Polyphenylene Sulfide	PDX 516	15	30	27,500	36,000	>30,000

Dimensional Tolerances as a Function of Filler
Content and Base Resin

Figure 13

Type	Amount % by wt.	Nylon 6/6		Polycarbonate	
		Total Composite Error (TCE) in $\times 10^{-4}$	Tooth-to-Tooth Error (TTE) in $\times 10^{-4}$	Total Composite Error (TCE) in $\times 10^{-4}$	Tooth-to-Tooth Error (TTE) in $\times 10^{-4}$
Glass Fibers	10	73	11	—	—
Glass Fibers	40	65	10	18	7
Glass Beads	30	27	6	7	4
Glass Fibers/TFE*	30/15	60	10	18	7
TFE	20	25	6	—	—

* Modified polytetrafluoroethylene lubricant

Figure 14

Gear Tolerance Charts

RF1008 (Fig.15)

DF1008 (Fig.16)

RF1006 B (Fig.17)

DF1006 B (Fig.18)

RFL4036 (Fig.19)

DFL4036 (Fig.20)

RL4040 (Fig.21)

NOTE: All runout checks start at the gate and finish at the gate.

Verticle scale - each square equals 0.0001 inches.

Figure 22

TYPICAL MOLDING CONDITIONS

Molding Parameters	RF-1008 40% G/R Nylon 6/6	DF-1006 30% G/R Polycarbonate
Injection Booster Pressure, psi	1,200	1,200
Injection Hold Pressure, psi	700	1,000
Injection Hold Time, seconds	5	5
Injection Booster Time, seconds	0.2	0.2
Mold Cure Time, seconds	10	10
Mold Open Time, seconds	2	2
Injection Rate, seconds	0.2	0.2
Screw RPM	100	100
Back Pressure, psi	50	50
Melt Temperature, °F	580	620
Mold Temperature, °F		
Stationary	140	180
Moving	140	180
Cushion, inch	1/16	1/16

Figure 23

Molding Variables	RF-1008		DF-1006	
	Total Composite Error (TCE) in $\times 10^{-4}$	Tooth-to-Tooth Error (ITE) in $\times 10^{-4}$	Total Composite Error (TCE) in $\times 10^{-4}$	Tooth-to-Tooth Error (ITE) in $\times 10^{-4}$
Typical Conditions	33	7	18	7
Lower injection pressure	26	7	18	7
Higher Injection Pressure	40	8	20	6
Slower Injection Rate	30	7	18	6
Shorter Holding Pressure	70	13	18	6
Longer Holding Pressure	43	5	18	5
Lower cylinder temperature	40	9	—	—
Higher cylinder temperature	46	6	13	5
No Cushion	50	6	19	6
Hotter Mold	48	8	—	—
Colder Mold	—	—	20	7

Standard Conditions
(DF1006)

Higher Cylinder Temp.
(DF1006)

(Figure 24)

Single Gate
(RF1008)

Triple Gate
(RF1008)

(Figure 25)

NOTE: All runout checks start at the gate and finish at the gate.

Figure 26

Tooth Strength as a Function of Molding Variables

Molding Variables	RF-1008	DF-1006
Typical Conditions	38,500	28,500
Lower Injection pressure	37,000	26,800
Higher Injection Pressure	38,800	28,400
Slower Injection Rate	35,800	25,800
Shorter Holding Pressure	37,000	27,000
Longer Holding Pressure	38,500	28,700
Lower cylinder temperature	38,800	—
Higher cylinder temperature	37,500	28,000
No Cushion	37,500	27,500
Hotter Mold	37,000	—
Colder Mold	—	28,800